

Safety Paradox in Ammonia-Fueled Vessels: CFD Study on Ventilation Effectiveness and Its Environmental Consequences

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Abstract. The International Maritime Organization (IMO)'s 2050 greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction strategy has identified ammonia as a promising carbon-neutral marine fuel. However, its toxicity and potential for accidental release introduce significant safety challenges. This study investigates ammonia gas dispersion from the Fuel Preparation Room (FPR) of an ammonia-fueled vessel using Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations. Scenarios were analyzed under two ventilation conditions: 30 air changes per hour (ACH) and 45 ACH. Indoor simulation results showed that increasing ventilation reduced the time to reach the AEGL-2 toxicity threshold from 21.2 seconds to 15.1 seconds. Peak ammonia concentrations reached approximately 20,000 ppm under 30 ACH and 14,000 ppm under 45 ACH—nearly 90 times higher than AEGL-2, representing a severe toxicity risk. However, these values were only about 13% and 9% of the Lower Flammable Limit (LFL), indicating that flammability was not the dominant hazard. Recovery to safe levels below 25 ppm required approximately 1-2 hours regardless of ventilation rate. Outdoor dispersion analysis further demonstrated that increased ventilation, while effective at reducing indoor concentrations, led to more rapid and extensive ammonia discharge to surrounding areas, impacting critical safety zones. These findings highlight a safety paradox in which ventilation intended to reduce one hazard may exacerbate another. The study underscores the limited effectiveness of ventilation alone and calls for complementary mitigation measures to address the toxicity risk posed by ammonia releases in marine applications.

Keywords: Ammonia-fueled ship, Fuel Preparation Room, Ventilation system, Gas dispersion analysis

1. Introduction

The greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction strategy of the International Maritime Organization (IMO) demands significant transformation in the shipping industry. In 2018, the IMO adopted the Initial Strategy under Resolution MEPC.304(72), establishing the goal of reducing GHG emissions from shipping by at least 50% by 2050 compared to 2008 levels [1]. Subsequently, in 2023, the IMO adopted the Revised Strategy under Resolution MEPC.377(80), aiming for Net-Zero GHG emissions by 2050 [2]. In response to these environmental regulations, decarbonization of ship propulsion systems has emerged as a critical challenge for the maritime industry.

In this context, ammonia (NH₃) has emerged as a promising carbon-neutral fuel for the maritime sector. It contains no carbon and produces no carbon dioxide during combustion when used as a primary fuel [3]. Although ammonia has lower energy density compared to liquefied natural gas (LNG), it offers practical advantages such as easier liquefaction compared to hydrogen and the potential to utilize some existing infrastructure.

However, ammonia possesses hazardous characteristics including toxicity, corrosiveness, and flammability, requiring stringent safety management. According to the Acute Exposure Guideline Levels (AEGL) established by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), AEGL-2 level (220 ppm for 10-30 minutes exposure) represents a concentration that could cause irreversible or serious health effects [4]. Additionally, the National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH) defines an ammonia Recommended Exposure Limit-Time Weighted Average (REL-TWA) of 25 ppm for an 8-hour workday, and an Immediately Dangerous to Life or Health (IDLH) threshold of 300 ppm, indicating the concentration at which exposure poses an immediate threat to life, health, or escape capability [5].

To ensure the safety of ammonia-fueled vessels, the IMO and various classification societies are developing safety regulations [6]. Ventilation systems in the fuel preparation room (FPR) play a crucial role in rapidly diluting and expelling leaked ammonia gas, aiming to maintain concentrations below toxic and flammable thresholds. Current regulations typically require 30 air changes per hour (ACH), which while effective in mitigating explosion hazards, may fall short in ensuring protection against acute toxic exposure, particularly in confined compartments.

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To address these ventilation-related safety challenges, recent studies have explored the effectiveness of increased air change rates. For instance, research by the Mærsk Mc-Kinney Møller Center for Zero Carbon Shipping (2023) indicates that increasing the ventilation rate from 30 ACH to 45 ACH can reduce ammonia-related risks on a tanker with semi-refrigerated ammonia fuel storage by approximately 5% in terms of cumulative risk exposure [7]. In line with these findings, major classification societies including ABS, DNV, and ClassNK have adopted a 45 ACH ventilation requirement [8][9][10]. While this enhanced ventilation requirement aims to reduce indoor concentrations more rapidly during ammonia leakage, its actual effectiveness in mitigating toxic exposure risks remains a subject requiring further detailed evaluation.

Jang et al. (2024) investigated ammonia gas dispersion and toxicity levels through vent mast using FLACS CFD analysis on a 31,000-dwt general cargo vessel model [11]. Their study analyzed various discharge scenarios considering current regulatory requirements, ventilation mast design, and environmental conditions. The results demonstrated that direct ammonia discharge through vent mast could pose fatal risks to crew in accommodation areas and potentially passengers onboard nearby vessels, even when complying with current regulatory requirements.

While previous studies have provided valuable insights, they often treated indoor and outdoor safety assessments in isolation, limiting their applicability to real-world leakage scenarios. This study addresses that gap by establishing ammonia leakage scenarios for the FPR of an ammonia-fueled gas carrier and presenting a methodology for the integrated analysis of indoor and outdoor dispersion characteristics. In particular, we quantitatively assess the trade-off between enhanced indoor safety and increased external environmental impact under different ventilation conditions (30 ACH and 45 ACH), systematically identifying the "Safety Paradox" phenomenon that has not been thoroughly addressed in existing research.

The main contributions of this study are fourfold:

(1) Development of an integrated CFD framework that uses indoor gas dispersion results as boundary conditions for outdoor dispersion modeling, simulating the entire sequence of actual leakage scenarios.

(2) Quantitative comparison of ventilation performance effects (30 ACH vs. 45 ACH) on both indoor safety and external environmental risk.

(3) Simultaneous evaluation of explosion and toxicity risks using the IEC 60079-10-1 standard [12] and AEGLE criteria.

(4) Provision of practical safety design guidance by assessing toxic impacts on key exposure points, such as accommodation areas, lifeboats, and engine room air intakes.

Ultimately, this research provides essential insights for regulatory development and supports the safe and sustainable deployment of ammonia as a marine fuel, contributing to the IMO's safety and environmental protection objectives.

2. Methodology

2.1. Overview of CFD Analysis

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations were performed using in:Flux CFD software v.3.21 [13] to evaluate gas dispersion behavior associated with ammonia leakage scenarios. To ensure both accuracy and computational efficiency, a hexahedral mesh was employed. The software provides automated mesh generation capabilities, significantly reducing pre-processing time while maintaining high mesh quality. An adaptive mesh refinement (AMR) strategy was applied to refine the mesh in regions with steep concentration gradients and complex flow patterns, optimizing computational resources while enhancing solution accuracy.

Boundary conditions were defined to realistically represent the indoor-to-outdoor dispersion scenario. Specifically, a velocity inlet was applied at the indoor source, while pressure outlet conditions were imposed at the outlet, lateral sides, and top of the domain. The bottom boundary was modeled as a no-slip wall to represent the floor structure. These conditions were selected to accurately capture flow paths and interactions between the confined and external environments.

Pressure-velocity coupling was handled using the SIMPLE (Semi-Implicit Method for Pressure-Linked Equations) algorithm. To account for buoyancy-driven transport caused by ammonia's density differences, the full buoyancy model, incorporating both thermal and concentration-driven effects, was adopted.

To resolve turbulent flow characteristics accurately, turbulence was modeled using the $k-\omega$ Shear Stress Transport (SST) model, a widely used two-equation eddy viscosity approach known for its robustness in both near-wall and free-stream conditions. The simulations were conducted under a transient (unsteady) framework to capture time-dependent gas dispersion behavior.

A second-order implicit backward Euler scheme was employed for temporal discretization, ensuring a balance between accuracy and stability. For spatial discretization, a second-order upwind scheme was used for convection terms, while a central differencing scheme was used for diffusive terms to minimize numerical dissipation.

To accurately and efficiently represent complex onboard geometries, the immersed boundary method (IBM) was employed to embed intricate structures into the Cartesian mesh without excessive refinement, thereby enhancing computational efficiency without compromising solution fidelity.

These combined numerical techniques and modeling strategies enabled robust and realistic simulation of ammonia dispersion dynamics within the integrated indoor–outdoor domain.

2.2. Indoor Gas Dispersion Modeling

The indoor gas dispersion analysis was conducted for a FPR. The ambient temperature was set at 35 °C. The computational domain was modeled based on the actual geometry of the FPR, including major equipment such as the Fuel Valve Unit (FVU). Plan and section views of a hexahedral mesh are provided in Figure 1. The hexahedral mesh was implemented to ensure efficient numerical analysis and accurate result derivation.

Figure 1. Plan (top) and Section (bottom) view of the hexahedral mesh in the FPR used for indoor CFD analysis, with major equipment labeled for reference.

The ventilation system consisted of a natural air supply and an exhaust with mechanical fan, which corresponded to 30 ACH. The boundary conditions were configured with pressure inlet conditions at the air supply opening and mechanical exhaust conditions at the ventilation exhaust.

To evaluate the influence of ventilation performance, a comparative analysis was performed by increasing the ventilation flow rate to 45 ACH, while maintaining the same mechanical configuration. The gas concentration variations at the ventilation exhaust and the size of flammable gas clouds were compared between the two conditions.

The Q9 volume, defined as the total volume of gas where concentrations fall within the flammable range (i.e., between the Lower Flammable Limits (LFL) and Upper Flammable Limits (UFL)), was used to assess the extent of flammable gas clouds. Although the Q9 method is widely applied to evaluate explosion hazards of hydrocarbon gases, its direct application to ammonia has limitations due to the narrower flammable range and relatively weak explosion characteristics of ammonia. Nonetheless, to conservatively evaluate the potential for forming an explosive atmosphere, the criterion suggested in the UK HSE report [14]—a stoichiometric flammable gas cloud with a characteristic dimension of 6 meters—was referenced. This dimension was approximated as a spherical cloud with a volume of approximately 113 m³ and used as a threshold for comparison.

The indoor leakage scenario considered in this study involved a release from the flange of the FVU on the liquid ammonia fuel supply line. The leak hole cross-sectional area was defined as 2.5 mm², based on the IEC 60079-10-1 standard [12], and the leakage direction was modeled vertically downward. The ammonia temperature at the release point and the initial peak leakage rate were estimated by using DNV Phast (Phast) v9.0.

Although the actual release is expected to be a two-phase flow, it was conservatively modeled as a single-phase gaseous release for simplification, ensuring a worst-case analysis from a toxic and flammability standpoint. The temporal release scenario assumed a 60-second delay from gas detection to Emergency Shutdown Valve (ESDV) activation, during which time ammonia would continue to leak. After shutdown, the remaining content within the isolatable section was assumed to fully discharge.

The simulation was conducted under transient conditions for a total of two hours following the leak event. Temporal and spatial discretization schemes were consistent with those described in Section 2.1, enabling time-resolved analysis of gas behavior and dispersion characteristics. The results provided ammonia concentration distributions and major dispersion pathways within the confined space.

By comparing simulation results under both ventilation scenarios, the impact of ventilation rate on explosive gas cloud development and dissipation was evaluated, yielding critical input for ventilation design and risk control strategies. Additionally, time-dependent ammonia concentrations at the ventilation exhaust were extracted and used as boundary conditions for the subsequent outdoor dispersion analysis described in Section 2.3.

2.3. Outdoor Gas Dispersion Modeling

The outdoor gas dispersion analysis was conducted on a simplified 3D representation of an ammonia-fueled gas carrier (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Plan view of the middle-sized gas carrier 3D model used for outdoor dispersion analysis, highlighting lifeboats, escape routes, and the FPR exhaust location.

The analysis utilized data derived from indoor gas dispersion simulations, with time-resolved ammonia emission characteristics at the mushroom vent outlet above the FPR serving as input conditions for the outdoor model. Exhaust flow rates were applied to reflect ventilation rates of 30 ACH and 45 ACH, respectively. The discharged gas composition was defined based on time-dependent ammonia concentration profiles extracted from the indoor simulation at the ventilation exhaust.

Atmospheric conditions were configured with an ambient temperature of 35°C and a relative wind velocity of 2.0 m/s. The wind direction was set from the bow toward the stern to reflect actual operational conditions. These environmental conditions were identified as key parameters influencing ammonia dispersion trajectories in the vicinity of the vessel.

Transient CFD simulations were performed over a two-hour period following the leakage event to ensure temporal consistency with the indoor analysis. While the same hexahedral mesh structure was used as in the indoor domain, the computational domain and boundary conditions were adapted to capture outdoor flow characteristics.

The design acceptance criterion for acute toxic exposure was established at 220 ppm, based on the CCC10 IGF Interim Guidelines. This concentration corresponds to the AEGL-2 threshold, defined as the level at which a 30-minute exposure could cause irreversible or serious health effects. Since the IGF guidelines specify concentration thresholds without clearly defined exposure durations, this study focused on the spatial extent of gas clouds exceeding 220 ppm. This threshold was considered a critical safety parameter from both design and operational standpoints.

The primary assessment criterion was whether the gas cloud reached critical receptors, including escape routes to accommodation areas, lifeboats, and engine air intakes. These locations are critical to crew safety during emergency evacuation and the continued operation of essential systems.

By comparing the spatial and temporal characteristics of outdoor gas dispersion under both ventilation scenarios (30 ACH vs. 45 ACH), the effect of enhanced ventilation on vessel safety was evaluated. The analysis specifically examined how the increased ventilation rate (45 ACH) influenced gas exposure risks at critical receptors and the spatial extent and persistence of regions exceeding the 220 ppm threshold.

2.4. Model Validation

To ensure the reliability of the CFD model developed in this study, simulation results were benchmarked against field-scale ammonia dispersion experiments conducted during the 1983 Desert Tortoise (DT) series experiment. These tests represent one of the most comprehensive and well-documented datasets for validating large-scale gas dispersion models.

As described in McGillivray et al. (2022), various research institutions modeled these experiments using Phast software [15]. Among them, DNV performed simulations of the DT1 experiment using Phast v8.61 with user-defined source terms to simulate the DT1 scenario. Key parameters are summarized in Table 1. These values were implemented in Phast to replicate the physical release conditions of the DT1 experiment.

Table 1. Key input and environmental parameters for DT1 ammonia dispersion experiment modeled by DNV using Phast v8.61.

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Value</i>	<i>Unit</i>	<i>Description</i>
Orifice diameter	0.081	m	Release point nozzle size
Release height	0.79	m	Vertical distance from ground
Exit temperature	21.5	°C	Ammonia jet temperature
Exit pressure	9.22	barg	Release pressure
Release rate	80.0	kg/s	Mass flow rate of ammonia
Release duration	126	s	Total release time
Wind speed (at 2 m)	7.42	m/s	Ambient wind velocity
Surface roughness length	0.003	m	Terrain roughness value
Stability class	D	–	Pasquill stability class
Ambient temperature	28.8	°C	Surrounding air temperature
Atmospheric pressure	0.909	bar	Site atmospheric pressure
Relative humidity	13.2	%	Ambient humidity level
Jet velocity (post-expansion)	90.3	m/s	Velocity from Phast expansion model
Liquid fraction	0.82	–	Two-phase composition
Mean droplet diameter	107	µm	From SMEDIS database

In the present study, the DT1 experiment was simplified by assuming a 100% gas-phase release and conducting steady-state simulations, representing a steady-state approximation at peak release conditions for simplicity and conservative assessment. This approach was adopted to reduce the computational complexity associated with two-phase flow while maintaining computational efficiency and core dispersion behavior. The CFD model replicated the experimental setup with maximum fidelity to boundary and ambient conditions.

Predicted ammonia concentration profiles were compared with experimental measurements at multiple downwind distances. Figure 3 compares the DT1 field data, Phast results, and the present CFD simulation. The model showed good agreement in terms of plume centerline concentration and horizontal dispersion width, with trends closely matching both the measured and Phast-predicted results.

Although a slight overprediction was observed at short distances (e.g., 100 m), the agreement improved significantly at longer distances (up to 800 m), indicating the model's reliability in predicting plume behavior over operationally relevant ranges.

These findings support the applicability of the proposed CFD modeling approach for ammonia dispersion analysis in maritime environments, particularly under emergency ventilation and leakage scenarios.

Figure 3. Comparison of ammonia concentration distributions from the DT1 field experiment, Phast simulations, and the present CFD analysis.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Indoor dispersion

The quantitative analysis of ammonia gas dispersion under two ventilation conditions (30 ACH and 45 ACH) provided valuable insights into the effectiveness of enhanced ventilation in mitigating ammonia-related hazards within the FPR. Figure 4 illustrates the temporal evolution of ammonia concentrations at the FPR ventilation exhaust for both scenarios. Dispersion behavior exhibited similar patterns in both cases, characterized by a rapid initial increase, a sustained plateau during continuous leakage, and a gradual decay after leakage cessation.

Figure 4. Ammonia concentration profiles at the FPR ventilation exhaust, comparing the time evolution under 30 ACH and 45 ACH conditions.

The time required for ammonia concentrations at the ventilation exhaust to reach the AEGL-2 threshold of 220 ppm was approximately 21.2 seconds under the 30 ACH condition and 15.1 seconds under the 45 ACH condition (Table 2). This indicates a reduction of approximately 6 seconds due to increased ventilation, though the practical advantage of such a short reduction is limited in an actual emergency scenario.

Furthermore, the intervals between reaching critical concentration thresholds (25 ppm, 220 ppm, and 300 ppm) were notably short in both scenarios, occurring within a narrow timeframe (approximately 13 to 23 seconds for 30

ACH, and 11 to 17 seconds for 45 ACH). This short timeframe implies that the intended sequential activation of alarms and safety protocols may instead become almost simultaneous, potentially diminishing the effectiveness of emergency response measures and increasing crew exposure risk.

Table 2. Time to reach key ammonia concentration thresholds (25, 220, 300 ppm) under 30 ACH and 45 ACH ventilation, showing minimal difference in response times.

<i>Threshold (ppm)</i>	<i>30 ACH</i>	<i>45 ACH</i>
25	13.2 sec	11.4 sec
220 (AEGL-2)	21.2 sec	15.1 sec
300	22.8 sec	16.2 sec

Peak ammonia concentrations exceeded the AEGL-2 threshold significantly under both ventilation conditions, reaching approximately 20,000 ppm with 30 ACH and approximately 14,000 ppm with 45 ACH. Despite the roughly 30% concentration reduction achieved by increasing ventilation, both cases still substantially exceeded the toxic threshold, demonstrating limited improvements in practical safety. Figure 4 also illustrates the spatial ammonia distribution at the peak release moment, with similar dispersion patterns and concentration gradients extending from the leak source to the exhaust outlet for both ventilation scenarios.

The recovery time—defined as the duration required for ammonia concentrations to decrease below the safe level of 25 ppm following leak termination—was approximately 1 to 2 hours for both ventilation rates. Thus, even substantial increases in ventilation rates (from 30 ACH to 45 ACH) did not meaningfully shorten the time needed to restore safe conditions in the FPR.

Figure 5 and Figure 6 compare the spatially averaged ammonia concentrations within the room to the exhaust concentrations. While the 45 ACH condition provided slightly more uniform mixing and marginally faster dilution, these minor improvements did not significantly mitigate overall toxicity risks. Ammonia concentrations consistently remained above AEGL-2 thresholds throughout most of the FPR during the active leakage period.

Figure 5. Comparison of spatially averaged and exhaust concentrations under 30 ACH, showing uniform distribution in FPR.

Figure 6. Comparison of spatially averaged and exhaust concentrations under 45 ACH, showing slightly improved mixing than 30 ACH.

Considering practical safety implications, the results indicate limited benefits from the 50% ventilation rate increase. Although measurable improvements were observed in peak concentrations and threshold attainment times, the overall risk profile remained largely unchanged. Both scenarios rapidly exceeded critical toxic thresholds and exhibited comparable recovery durations.

Explosion hazards were evaluated using the Q9 criterion, defined as the volume of gas within concentrations between 25% and 100% of the LFL, according to the UK HSE report [14]. Calculated Q9 volumes were 0.042 m³ at 30 ACH and 0.027 m³ at 45 ACH, indicating a modest 36% reduction with higher ventilation. However, both cases resulted in extremely localized and minimal explosion hazards, limited to small areas near the leak source.

These comprehensive findings demonstrate that simply increasing ventilation rates is insufficient as a standalone strategy for effectively managing ammonia leakage risks. Although marginal reductions in peak concentrations and slight improvements in response times were noted, the persistently high toxic concentrations and prolonged recovery durations underscore the limitations of relying solely on ventilation enhancement. Additionally, higher ventilation rates entail increased energy use, space requirements, and system complexity, which may outweigh the modest safety improvements observed.

Consequently, this study emphasizes the necessity for an integrated approach to safety, incorporating supplementary mitigation measures beyond ventilation improvements alone. Enhanced gas detection systems, automated emergency shutdown mechanisms, and targeted mitigation technologies are critical components to effectively minimize toxic exposure risks and improve overall crew safety onboard ammonia-fueled vessels.

3.2. Outdoor dispersion

Based on the time-dependent ammonia concentration profiles extracted from the indoor simulations, a two-hour outdoor dispersion analysis was conducted to evaluate the behavior of the ammonia-air mixture released through the ventilation exhaust of the FPR. The Acute Exposure Guideline Level-2 (AEGL-2) threshold of 220 ppm was adopted as the primary criterion for evaluating toxic impacts on surrounding areas.

At approximately 60 seconds, when the Emergency Shutdown Valve (ESDV) is activated and the leakage is terminated, ammonia gas clouds exceeding the AEGL-2 threshold were observed forming prominently in the space between the top of the FPR and the accommodation area. Notably, the catwalk connecting the FPR to the accommodation was already affected by this stage. In both the 30 ACH and 45 ACH cases, the gas cloud distributions at this time were nearly identical, indicating that increasing ventilation capacity does not significantly mitigate early-stage external dispersion. These results are illustrated in Figure 7 and Figure 8.

Figure 7. Ammonia cloud at 62 seconds under 30 ACH, forming between the FPR and accommodation via the catwalk.

Figure 8. Ammonia cloud at 62 seconds under 45 ACH, with similar distribution to the 30 ACH.

Between approximately 137 and 161 seconds, the AEGL-2 level gas clouds reached the lifeboat area of the accommodation. During this period, the catwalk and escape routes leading from the FPR to the accommodation were also impacted. The spatial extent and concentration levels of the gas clouds remained similar in both ventilation scenarios, suggesting that the increased ventilation rate provided minimal benefit in terms of reducing the toxic exposure risk at critical evacuation points. These observations are presented in Figure 9 and Figure 10.

Figure 9. Ammonia cloud at 161 seconds under 30 ACH reaching the lifeboat and escape route.

Figure 10. Ammonia cloud at 137 seconds under 45 ACH impacting critical zones earlier than with 30 ACH.

At approximately 600 seconds, large ammonia gas clouds with concentrations exceeding the AEGL-2 threshold were observed completely covering the accommodation area and extending well beyond the stern of the vessel. This extensive spread occurred under both ventilation conditions and demonstrated similar trends in terms of spatial reach and intensity. The results suggest that increasing the ventilation rate alone is insufficient to contain the spread of toxic gas in the external environment. The persistent presence of hazardous concentrations over a broad area indicates a strong need for supplementary mitigation strategies. These results are visualized in Figure 11 and Figure 12.

Figure 11. At 600 seconds under 30 ACH, showing the cloud fully covering all critical receptors.

Figure 12. At 600 seconds under 45 ACH, similar patterns persist, showing larger cloud between FPR and accommodation.

After 1000 seconds, AEGL-2 level concentrations began to dissipate around the lifeboat area; however, meaningful concentrations persisted along the escape routes leading to the accommodation. Although the overall volume of the gas cloud gradually decreased over time, the presence of residual toxic concentrations still posed a risk to evacuation paths. The dispersion patterns and decay behavior were comparable between the two ventilation cases, further reinforcing the limited impact of increased ventilation capacity on long-term external toxic gas management. These findings are depicted in Figure 13 and Figure 14.

Figure 13. Ammonia dispersion at 1030 seconds under 30 ACH, the cloud clears the lifeboat area but remains along the escape routes.

Figure 14. Ammonia dispersion at 1020 seconds under 45 ACH, with similar pattern but shorter extent than the 30 ACH.

Overall, these findings indicate that enhanced ventilation performance has only a limited effect on controlling the spread of toxic ammonia concentrations in the external environment. Critical areas such as lifeboats, accommodation, and escape routes are exposed to hazardous concentrations within a short time, and these concentrations can persist for an extended period. Relying solely on increased ventilation is therefore insufficient for effective risk mitigation. Complementary safety measures—including early leak detection, automatic shutdown valves, and localized neutralization or dilution systems—are essential for ensuring crew safety during ammonia leakage events on board ammonia-fueled vessels.

4. Conclusion

This study conducted a quantitative assessment of the safety implications of ventilation performance in ammonia-fueled vessels, focusing on gas dispersion behavior following a leakage event in the FPR. Two ventilation conditions—30 and 45 ACH—were compared using CFD simulations to evaluate both indoor and outdoor dispersion characteristics. The outdoor analysis was coupled with time-dependent ammonia concentrations obtained from indoor simulations, and the AEGL-2 threshold of 220 ppm was applied as the primary toxic impact criterion.

The indoor analysis showed that increasing the ventilation rate from 30 to 45 ACH reduced the peak ammonia concentration by approximately 30% and shortened the time to reach the AEGL-2 level by 5 seconds. However, the time to reach toxic concentrations was extremely short—on the order of tens of seconds—and the recovery time (to drop below 25 ppm) remained similar at approximately 1–2 hours for both cases. In addition, the volume of the flammable gas cloud, defined using the Q9 criterion, was highly localized and posed minimal explosion risk in both ventilation scenarios.

The outdoor analysis revealed that immediately after leakage termination (around 60 seconds), ammonia gas clouds exceeding the AEGL-2 threshold formed along the escape route between the FPR and accommodation area. Within a few minutes, these clouds reached critical zones such as the accommodation and lifeboat areas. At 600 seconds, the gas cloud fully covered the accommodation and extended well beyond the vessel stern. Even after 1000 seconds, toxic concentrations persisted along the escape routes. The dispersion behavior and toxic impact range were similar under both ventilation conditions, highlighting the limited effectiveness of increased ventilation in reducing outdoor exposure risk.

Overall, the results indicate that while increasing the ventilation rate from 30 to 45 ACH provided some localized benefits in reducing peak concentrations, it had only marginal effects in mitigating toxic risks based on the AEGL-2 criterion. Moreover, the outdoor results demonstrated a safety paradox, in which improved ventilation accelerated the release of toxic gas into the external environment, thereby increasing the potential for human exposure. These findings suggest that ventilation enhancement alone is insufficient for comprehensive safety assurance, and the implementation of additional safety measures is essential.

This study contributes a scientifically grounded framework for evaluating the effectiveness of ventilation systems and safety design strategies for ammonia-fueled ships by integrating indoor and outdoor dispersion scenarios. Future research should consider a wider range of operational conditions, including variable wind directions and weather patterns, as well as multiple incident scenarios, to further support regulatory development and vessel design optimization.

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